

CREATIVE IN-SERVICE CLASSROOM LEARNING TEACHING IN ENGLISH

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Annotation. The article's abstract discusses the idea of "professional development" in English teaching. In modern studies on methods of teaching English language, increasing attention is focused on professional development. Professional development is defined as the recognition of the significance of improving the caliber and applicability of education and learning.

Аннотация. В аннотации статьи рассматривается идея «профессионального развития» в преподавании английского языка. В современных исследованиях методики преподавания английского языка все большее внимание уделяется профессиональному развитию. Профессиональное развитие определяется как признание важности повышения уровня и применимости образования и обучения.

Annotatsiya. Maqolaning annotatsiyasida ingliz tilini o'qitishda "kasbiy rivojlanish" g'oyasi muhokama qilinadi. Ingliz tilini o'qitish metodikasi bo'yicha zamonaviy tadqiqotlarda professional rivojlanishga e'tibor kuchaymoqda. Kasbiy rivojlanish ta'lim va ta'limning malakasi va qo'llanilishini yaxshilash muhimligini tan olish sifatida belgilanadi.

Keywords: *professional development, online communication, online presentation, the task-based approach, the project-based approach, self-confidence, self-efficacy.*

Ключевые слова: *профессиональное развитие, онлайн-коммуникация, онлайн-презентация, целенаправленный подход, проектный подход, уверенность в себе, самоэффективность.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *kasbiy rivojlanish, onlayn muloqot, onlayn taqdimot, vazifaga asoslangan yondashuv, loyihaga asoslangan yondashuv, o'ziga ishonch, o'zini rivojlantirish.*

One of the main determinants for enhancing the quality and relevance of education and learning is considered to be professional development. It has long been a major form of professional development for pre-service and in-service teachers in developing.

Many teachers can learn new skills, advance their careers, and eventually start teaching online thanks to professional development. However, if you are used to printing paper books and printed worksheets, it must be difficult to cut flashcards operating online. There are so many questions teachers have: How to start teaching online? What would I need? How to arrange work for pairs? How will additional materials be used? How to teach? Our approach has been to offer learning opportunities and evaluate a specific form of online communication, the online presentation, which will be covered in more detail shortly.

We are building a culture of innovation as our educators of the future, in which our academic staff will be empowered to use new technology to advance their teaching practices. The conventional design of the curriculum and training of the class centered on the subjects considered beneficial to learners. This meant that the grammar and vocabulary that educators felt learners ought to know were learned by learners. The feedback from learners was scarce, to say the least. What we learned from this is why it is important to build lesson plans for activities that can be comfortable for all learners to relate to. The task-based approach reflects a major paradigm shift as the emphasis has shifted from content to skills and competencies. Architecture and planning, then, are not about what is being learned but about why it is being taught. In order

to teach teachers, the material they need to achieve their goals and objectives, this approach separates individual skills and competencies.

Similar to the task-based approach, the project-based approach is intended to fulfill learners' specific needs by adapting language to the skills and competencies they currently require individually and professionally. The implementation of this method begins by defining the one, global objective that the individual or group of learners has.

Given the nature of their jobs, I naturally taught them differently than I would have if I had been teaching someone who wanted to learn how to have casual conversations in English. In their office, they were required to create specific monthly reports in English for various departments. Thus, we divided a sample report into sections and examined each one separately. The sections were prepared by each instructor as though they were authentic.

In class, in addition to covering all the vocabulary and grammar necessary to complete each section, I addressed the difficulties my teachers experienced. Their final project was a full report that they must apply for approval to their supervisor, and their company handbook was based on the requirements we used to build the report. It was a lot of work, but with it, we had fun. But what if you have a class full of adults who, to start with, do not want to be in class because of their poor English especially online lesson? Start by doing an evaluation of need, looking at what they are interested in and what topics they really need to know. This evaluation will contribute to the creation of one overall project that will become the end product of the class. From an online presentation to a large-scale production like a class play, this project can be anything. Whatever the case, individual tasks that lead learners to the objectives in the evaluation must be part of the project. I think of the project as their final, thorough evaluation. Whereas cumulative evaluations are small tests or the completion of individual assignments. Just remember, your criteria for assessment must be clear so that teachers know what they are graded on. I think individual tasks enhance participants' self-confidence and self-efficacy as teachers. This induces a stronger belief in their own power and increased willingness and ability to take risks and try new methods and tools. This can enhance teaching and learning experience, efficiency, and lead to higher achievements. Academics are also more willing to adapt into their teaching good practices that they enjoyed as learners. Using a variety of innovative tools – such as multimedia materials, online courses, active learning, and peer mentoring – provides academics with a clear vision of the best and most suitable practices for their course.

Higher education systems around the world are facing new tendencies. One of them is resulting in the spread of a student-centered approach and the growing importance of modern digital technologies. The advantages and disadvantages of these changes are disputable. But in the wake of these changes, academic professionalism has undoubtedly become more important and is now necessary for both career advancement and the institution's ability to compete.

References:

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